

EMULGEL: AN EXTENSIVE ANALYSIS OF A POTENTIAL TOPICAL MEDICATION DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Delivering drugs through the skin is an effective method for a variety of therapeutic agents, and emulgels are increasingly being explored as an innovative and promising formulation option. These advanced systems effectively merge the advantageous properties of emulsions and gels, with numerous studies highlighting their enhanced skin penetration capabilities. The dual composition of emulgels enables efficient delivery of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs, addressing the limitations commonly associated with traditional topical formulations. Reducing the size of emulsion globules through nanonization and micronization can significantly improve stability and extend the duration of emulgel half-life. In addition, wide range of benefits linked to emulgels highlights their strong potential as an optimal system for topical drug delivery. This article presents a comprehensive overview of emulgels, detailing their fundamental components, standard formulation techniques, evaluation parameters, and future prospects, while also highlighting notable marketed products that emphasize their increasing relevance in contemporary dermatological practice.

KEYWORDS: Emulsion, Gel, Emulgel, Topical delivery.

INTRODUCTION

Applying a formulation containing medication to the skin in order to address a cutaneous ailment is referred to as topical medication administration. When an alternate drug delivery method (oral, sublingual, rectal, and parental) don't work, this approach is employed. Regarding both local and systemic disorders, subject medication delivery is a popular therapeutic approach. The medication is taken up by the skin and gets to the location of the action in the topical delivery system to produce a therapeutic effect. The physiological characteristics of the carrier have an immediate effect on rate of release of drugs from a topical preparation. The topical delivery method's main advantage is that it circumvents first-pass metabolism.^[1]

Emulgel: Emulgel is the term used when gel and emulsion are used together. The most promising drug delivery method for both hydrophilic and hydrophobic medications is emulgel. Emulgel is an intriguing topical medication delivery technology that combines an

emulsion and gel release control mechanism. Solid, liquid, semi-solid, and other preparations are among the topical medication delivery methods that are primarily categorized according to their consistencies. Emulgel is a formulation that combines gel and emulsion; the kind of mixture used relies on the drug's nature to get the highest bioavailability.^[2,3]

Figure 1: Structure of Emulgel.

ADVANTAGES^[4,5]

- Compared to traditional products, Emulgel also offers better patient compliance.
- It assists in avoiding undesirable gastrointestinal responses and avoiding the first pass metabolism.
- Emulgel can also offer regulated release of the active components, extending the medication's half-life.
- By combining the advantages of gel and emulsion in a single formulation, Emulgel enhances the stability and drug release profile of the lipophilic medication.
- Emulgels are economical since their production costs are lower than those of other dosage forms.

Figure 2: Advantages of Emulgel.

DISADVANTAGES^[6]

- Higher molecular weight and particle size medications cannot be absorbed through the skin.
- Occasionally, tiny bubbles may appear in Emulgel.

Figure 3: Formulation of emulgels.

Different types of emulgel^[10]

Based on the size of their particles, emulgels can be divided into three primary groups: macroemulgel, nanoemulgel, and microemulgel.

1. Macroemulgel

- Particle Size: Greater than 400 nm.
- Appearance: Opaque and homogeneous.
- Microscopic Observation: Emulsion droplets are easily detectable due to their large size.
- Stability: Thermodynamically unstable.
- Usage: Most widely used type of emulgel.

2. Nanoemulgel

- Preparation: Formed by incorporating nanoemulsion into a gel.

- Decreases the drug's penetrability.
- Another common occurrence is skin irritation.

Factors Influencing Topically Applied Products' Penetrability and Absorption^[7,8]

- 1) Hydration of the Skin
- 2) The Vascularity
- 3) The Lipid Level
- 4) Skin pH
- 5) Follicle Density of Hair
- 6) Density of Sweat Glands
- 7) The skin's inflammation
- 8) Lipid Composition
- 9) Coefficients of Partition
- 10) Molecular Mass
- 11) Level of Ionization
- 12) Vehicle Types
- 13) Drug concentration

Methods for Increasing the Rate of Penetration and Absorption^[9]

- 1) Chemical Improvement
- 2) Physical Improvement
- 3) Biochemical Improvement
- 4) Supersaturation improvement

Formulation of Emulgel

Emulgels contain several excipients that aid in their formulation and improve their properties. The key excipients used in emulgel include.

- Particle Size: Less than 100 nm.
- Appearance: Transparent and homogeneous.
- Stability: Thermodynamically stable dispersion.
- Advantages: Achieves better permeability due to smaller droplet size.

3. Microemulgel

- Particle Size: Between 10 and 100 nanometers.
- Stability: Thermodynamically stable formulation.
- Composition: Designed to facilitate drug penetration across the skin to the targeted site.
- Advantages: Overcomes constraints of gels and microemulsions. Offers high viscosity, good permeability, and homogeneity compared to traditional topical therapies.

Components of Emulgel^[11,13]

Aqueous Material

Aqueous materials are critical components in emulsion formulations, forming the aqueous phase. The most commonly utilized aqueous materials are:

- **Water:** This is the primary and most fundamental aqueous material. It serves as a solvent for water-soluble ingredients and creates the dispersed or continuous phase in emulsions of water in oil (W/O) or oil in water (O/W). Its purity is often a key consideration in pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.
- **Alcohol:** Alcohols, particularly ethanol, are frequently used in conjunction with or as a partial replacement for water in the aqueous phase. They can:
 - Enhance solubility: Dissolve certain drugs or excipients that have limited solubility in water alone.
 - Aid penetration: Facilitate the penetration of active components into the skin.
 - Provide cooling sensation: This is particularly noticeable with volatile alcohols.
 - Act as a preservative: In some concentrations, alcohols can have antimicrobial properties.

Oils

Oils form the crucial oily phase of emulsions, with mineral oils being the most commonly employed for emulgel development, either by itself or in conjunction with additional oils, such as soft and hard paraffin. Additionally, castor oil is sometimes incorporated due to its laxative properties, while other oils, including jojoba oil, arachis oil (peanut oil), cottonseed oil, maize oil, and fish liver oil, are utilized for their diverse medicinal benefits

Emulsifiers

The most crucial components for maintaining emulsion stability, typically functioning as surfactants in the emulsification process. For oil-in-water (O/W) emulsions, nonionic surfactants with a Hydrophilic-Lipophilic Balance (HLB) value higher than 8 are commonly used, such as Tweens (e.g., Tween 80, HLB approx. 15.0) and certain Spans (though Spans like Span 80 have a low HLB and are generally for W/O emulsions, they can be part of an O/W blend).

Conversely, for water-in-oil (W/O) emulsions, surfactants with an HLB less than 8 are utilized, with mineral oils themselves having a low HLB. Some widely used emulsifiers include PEG 40 stearate (HLB approx. 17.3 for O/W), Span 80 (HLB approx. 4.3 for W/O), Tween 80 (HLB approx. 15.0 for O/W), Stearic acid (often used as a co-emulsifier for O/W, with a required HLB of around 15 as an emulsifier), and Sodium stearate (HLB approx. 16-18 for O/W).

Gelling agents

Gelling agents are substances primarily employed to improve consistency and viscosity of a formulation, effectively acting as thickening agents to create a gel-like structure.

Preservatives

Preservatives are essential components used in emulgels to protect them from microbial contamination and growth, thereby extending their shelf life and ensuring their safety for use. Common examples include propyl paraben and methyl paraben.

Figure 4. components of emulgel.

Emulgel Preparation Method^[14,16]

Step 1: Preparation of emulsion

a) Oil phase preparation: Propylene glycol is dissolved in a light paraffin solvent to create emulsion's oil phase. the oil phase of the emulsion.

b) Aqueous phase preparation: The aqueous phase was created by dissolving the drug in ethanol. Upon heating the oil and aqueous phases independently to 75°C, the aqueous phase was continuously agitated as the oil phase was gradually added until it reached room temperature.

Step 2: Gel preparation

Polymers like carbapol 934 were dissolved in filtered water while being continuously stirred to create the gel base. The pH and amoderate speed are adjusted to 2–6 with triethanolamine (TEA).

Step 3: Formulation of Emulgel

The emulsion is combined with the gel foundation while being gently stirred.

Figure 5. Preparation of Emulgel.

Evaluation Parameters

1. Physical examination^[17,18]

The emulgel's pH, homogeneity, color, consistency, and appearance are evaluated by visual examination. A pH meter measures the pH value using a 1% water solution of the emulgel.

2. pH Determination^[18,19]

Using a digital pH meter, the emulgel's pH is determined. A topical product works well with the skin. Knowing the product's pH helps ensure it is compatible with the skin

3. Determination of viscosity^[20,21]

Using an appropriate viscometer, the emulgel's viscosity is determined. We can study how temperature and pressure affect the viscosity by changing the shear rate and storage temperature. This helps us understand how the product's consistency changes when stored at different temperatures and how it behaves when applied with different amounts of force.

4. Extrudability^[22,23]

Extrudability is an essential property of topical gel formulations, and it can be evaluated by determining the amount of force needed to remove the gel from a tube. To assess the extrudability of a gel formulation, a gentle finger pressure is applied to the tube, and the percentage of gel that is extruded is measured. The extrudability of the gel formulations can be evaluated in accordance with the protocol. Compared to sodium CMC gel, Carbopol and HPMC gels found to have superior extrudability.

5. Rheological Studies^[24,25]

The viscosity of the prepared batches is accurately measured utilizing a Brookfield Viscometer equipped with a spindle 07. Prior to measurement, the formulation under evaluation is carefully poured into a beaker and

allowed to settle for 30 minutes at the designated assay temperature. Subsequently, spindle is dropped into the emulgel's center perpendicularly, ensuring optimal measurement conditions.

6. Study of In-vitro Drug Release^[26,27]

The Franz Diffusion Cell is employed to investigate and contrast with the *in-vitro* release characteristics of various formulations, utilizing inert membranes that serve as simplified models of human skin. These membranes possess a porous substructure composed of a hydrophobic matrix, rendering them suitable for this purpose. Although the permeability of these membranes to pharmaceuticals is higher than that of human skin, the data generated nonetheless provide valuable insights into the relative permeabilities of different formulations. To conduct the experiment, synthetic membrane pieces are immersed in a 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer for 24 hours, after that carefully mount it in a Franz-type diffusion cell. Ensure that the membrane is securely positioned and free of any air bubbles. On the donor side of the diffusion cell, apply 200 mg of the sample, ensuring that it completely covers the membrane.

Submerge the entire assembly in a water bath maintained at 32°C. Ensure that the assembly is vigorously stirred throughout the experiment to maintain uniform conditions. At predetermined intervals, carefully remove 2 mL samples from the receiver compartment. Replace each sample with a comparable amount of fresh buffer to keep the experiment's integrity. Perform spectrophotometric analysis on all collected samples to determine the content of drug release at a specific wavelength.

7. Skin irritation Test^[28]

The skin irritation test, commonly referred to as patch test, is a critical evaluation tool designed to assess the potential of an emulgel to cause skin irritation or cutaneous reactions. Laboratory animals, typically rats, mice, or rabbits, are prepared for the test by shaving a specific area of their skin. The exposed skin area is then treated with the emulgel product, and any adverse skin changes are carefully observed and recorded. The product is considered to have a high potential for causing skin irritation if, after a predetermined period, the treated skin area exhibits signs of irritation, such as redness, inflammation, or other adverse reactions.

8. Ex-vivo Drug Release Study^[29,31]

Obtain a skin sample from a Wistar male rat and carefully slice it, ensuring the dorsal side faces upwards. Clamp the skin slice to the hollow glass tube's one end of modified diffusion cell, securing it firmly in place. Evenly apply a uniform layer of Emulgel to the membrane, ensuring complete coverage. Prepare a pH 5.5 phosphate buffer to serve as the dissolving medium for the drug release study. Assemble the diffusion cell by bringing the receptor compartment and donor compartment into contact. Allow the system to equilibrate before initiating the drug release study.

9. Swelling index^[32]

Place 1 g of the emulgel on a piece of porous aluminum foil, ensuring even distribution. Store the emulgel sample in a 50 ml beaker with 10 ml of sodium hydroxide (0.1

N) solution. At various time intervals, carefully remove the emulgel sample from the beaker and place it in a dry area for a short period. Weigh the swelled emulgel sample (wt) and record the value. Calculate the swelling index using the following formula:

$$\text{Swelling Index (SW \%)} = [(wt - wo) / wo] \times 100$$

Where, Wt = Weight of swollen emulgel after time t,

Wo = Initial weight of emulgel at zero time

(SW) % = Percent swelling Index

10. Kinetic Modeling^[33]

Ex-vivo permeation test data is fitted into a variety of mathematical models to assess the drug release kinetics, including:

1. Zero-order model
2. First-order model
3. Higuchi model

The coefficient of determination (R²) is used to assess each model's goodness of fit. The best fit is indicated by the model with the highest R² value, which is closest to 1 and is considered the optimal model for describing the drug release kinetic.

11. Stability study^[34]

Fill 5g aluminum collapsible tubes with the emulgel formulation, ensuring that the tubes are properly sealed. Storage Conditions Place the filled tubes in stability chambers maintained at the following conditions:

1. Refrigerated conditions: 5°C
2. Ambient conditions: 25°C/60% relative humidity (RH)
3. Elevated temperature conditions: 30°C/65% RH

MARKETED EMULGEL FORMULATION

Table 1: Marketed emulgel formulation for different brands.

Sl. No	Brand Name	Active Ingredient	Manufacture
1.	Acent gel	Capsaicin, aceclofenac	Intra labs India Pvt Ltd
2.	Adwiflam emulgel	Diclofenac diethylamine	Saja pharmaceuticals
3.	Benzolait emulgel	Benzoyl peroxide & biguanide	Roydermal
4.	Nadicin cream	Nadifloxacin	Psychoremedies
5.	Lupigyl gel	Metronidazole	Lupin pharma
6.	Zortene	Tazarotene	Elder pharmaceuticals
7.	Avindo gel	Azithromycin	Cosme pharmaceuticals
8.	Emulgel	Miconazole nitrate	Medical union
9.	Derma feet	Urea	Herbitas
10.	Excex gel	Adapalene, clindamycin	Zee laboratories
11.	Levorag emulgel	Hibiscus, liquorice	THD Ltd.

Future Scenario of Emulgel

A recent revolution in this field is being sparked by the use of nanotechnology to nanonize and micronize emulsion particles, leading to the creation of emulgels with improved drug penetrability and bioavailability.^[35] The other benefits of emulgels such as controlled release application, rapid drug release, better drug loading capacity etc. are indicating towards development of more efficient and productive formulation and it is expected to appear as ideal approach for the delivery of various drugs in future.^[36,37]

CONCLUSION

According to the economic success of currently available emulgel products, this method has the potential to replace the majority of traditional systems for topical drug delivery and aid in improving drug absorption and bioavailability. Furthermore, when compared to both parent products—emulsions and gels—emulgel exhibits superior drug loading capability and stability. Additionally, the current emulgel restrictions will be addressed by the introduction of nanotechnology, and it is anticipated that this technology will be used to formulate more better formulations. Along with this, the structure of the skin is enhancing emulgel's penetration

ability, and the discovery of novel permeation enhancers is thought to increase the therapeutic efficacy of medications when taken in the form of emulgel. There is currently a great need for innovative formulations due to the incapacity of traditional therapy to deliver lipophilic medications via topical route. Emulgels are currently meeting all of the requirements and, as a result, covering a wide variety of indications. As a result, emulgel's current benefits and anticipated future developments are encouraging its inclusion in clinical trials and making it a great substitute for topical drug delivery. A number of medications, such as NSAIDs, antimicrobials, and antifungal agents, are anticipated to be administered as emulgels in the future.

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